

Media and Communication Plan

Deliverable D5.3

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1. Abstract

The Media and Communication Plan (MCP) describes the communication structures implemented to steer the communication between the project and all potential stakeholders and multiple audiences providing targeted information for each identified audience.

The background for this document is to be found in the Art. 38.1 of the Grant Agreement Communication activities by beneficiaries: „*The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner*“.

The Media and Communication plan represents the project strategy for:

- Communicating the results of our research to a number of audiences we have identified in the document and with an adequate number and choice of communication tools
- Promoting the project and its results beyond the project’s own community
- Promoting interaction with selected audiences

The Plan also indicates 1) which audiences we target and 2) which communication measures are adopted to open a dialogue with these audiences.

A special section of the MCP is also dedicated to communication tools adopted within the consortium to ensure internal information flow and exchange and thus foster a smooth and integrated implementation of the activities described in the Description of the Action.

2. Conclusion and Results

The MCP is attached here as an annex. This document is the starting point for the implementation of the media and communication strategy of the project. Updates of this plan are foreseen in the progress reports.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The scope of the present text is to highlight in which framework the MCP has been established.

4.1 Why a Media and Communication Plan?

While drafting the Media and Communication Plan, we had to take into account the framework of obligations we need to comply with the following.

Grant Agreement Art. 38.1 Communication activities by beneficiaries

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

Grant Agreement 38.1.2 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text: For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 675191”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Grant Agreement 38.1.3 Disclaimer excluding the Commission responsibility

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DoA: Task 5.5 Communication [Lead: DKRZ. Participants: ECMWF] and the section 2.2.3. in particular the table 2.2b

The communication activities of the project will involve all consortium partners and their respective staff, including researchers. The project office (PO) with the Scientific Officer (SO) is central part of the activities.

As indicated in the table in Section 2.2.3, we have already foreseen tools for the implementation of our communication strategy; a Media and Communication Plan [D5.3] focusing on the most suitable tools for the most suitable audiences will be set up in PM2 of the project and regularly updated by the Project Office. We have identified different levels of communication activities:

- Communication activities to promote the project and its findings (ref. to Section 2.2.3 for more details). The website will be set up in PM2 [D5.2].
- Coordination of internal communication within the consortium, between work packages and partner with the supporters, the user group committee and the scientific advisory board (SAB);
- Communication with other EU funded projects and the European Commission.

As indicated in the section 2.2b table of the DoA, in the project proposal we had already foreseen a number of tools for the implementation of our communication strategy.

4.2 Who is responsible for the MCP implementation?

The communication element of the project will involve **all consortium partners** and their respective staff, including researchers. The lead will be with DRKZ and ECMWF.

The project office (PO) and the Scientific Officer (SO) are also central players in the implementation of the plan.

The partners in the project have **professional communication and public engagement officers** in their organizations, and we will take advantage of their network.

4.3 Target audiences

The strategy identifies different types of audiences - they determine the relevant media use as communication channel to open a dialogue.

In the DoA ¹we had already identified the following audiences: General public, Climate research institutions and National weather services, Wider scientific community, HPC industry, ETP4HPC, European Commission (as a multiplier).

After careful consideration, we have grouped these audiences in three groups and identified different levels of communication activities²:

1. Stakeholders who have **a specific interest** in this project's outcomes
2. Media and general public who might have a general interest
3. Project partners

Thus we have come up with the following matrix.

¹ Table 2.2b: Overview of ESIWACE main communication and tools. The list was not exhaustive.

² As indicated in DoA, in WP5 /Task 5.5, in section 2.2.3 and Table 2.2a and 2.2b.

Type of communication	Audiences	Scope of the communication
Stakeholder communication	Stakeholders who have a specific interest in this project's outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) • User Group Committee (UGC) • Supporters • Scientific NWP and climate research community • Business sector • Other scientific networks beyond ESIWACE community • Policy makers • European Commission services • EU funded projects, networks and initiatives 	Ensuring dissemination of the results and further exploitation of our results outside the consortium group (³)
General communication	Media and general public who might have a general interest	Promoting the project and its findings
Project internal communication	Project partners (i.e. beneficiaries of the grant)	Ensuring smooth exchange of information, project implementation and management

4.4 Contents of Media and Communication Plan

For different types of audiences, we have identified the following:

- Specific goals of the communication measures
- Language register
- Tools: list of best communication tools tailored for the specific audience
- Potential contents
- Frequency
- Responsibilities within the consortium

For each communication tool, we have provided a short description and a number of possible indicators for monitoring the outcome of the activity. Some of these tools are already operative.

4.5 Time coverage of the Media and Communication Plan

The MCP cover the entire project from month 1 to the end closure of its activities (31 Aug. 2019). Following the EC Guidelines⁴, communication measures will be implemented during the period of the grant and thus stop with the project closure, but dissemination of results continue after that date. This will be taken in consideration in the **Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.5)**.

³ As Alexandra Ruete of the EC indicates: "Dissemination (GA article 29) is a separate obligation (e.g. through scientific articles and conferences)." The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.5) of ESIWACE will be made available in month 12.

⁴ European IPR Helpdesk, Managing H2020 projects to maximise impact and innovation, Dr. Eugene Sweeney, 8th July 2015

Figure 1: Timeline for Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation activities. Source (EU IPR Helpdesk)

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- European Commission, "Communicating EU Research and Innovation, A guidance for project participants, Version 1.0", EU Publications Office, Luxembourg, 2014
- Annotated GA (version July 2014, p. 217)
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation European Commission, PowerPoint presentation on "Communicating Horizon 2020 projects" Alexandra Ruete, 2015
- European IPR Helpdesk, PowerPoint presentation on "Managing H2020 projects to maximise impact and innovation", Dr. Eugene Sweeney, 8th July 2015
- EU Project Websites – Best Practice Guidelines
https://ec.europa.eu/research/.../pdf/project_website_guidelines_en.pdf

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

These are the publications of those involved in this deliverable. These are inputs we upload in the European Commission database.

Not applicable.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:
 The Media and Communication Plan will be made available to the public on the website www.esiwace.eu and to the beneficiaries in the intranet.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

9. Efforts for this deliverable

Person-months spent on this deliverable:

Beneficiary	Person-months	Period covered
DKRZ	1	01 Sept. 2015 – 31 Oct. 2015
ECMWF	0	01 Sept. 2015 – 31 Oct. 2015
CRNS-IPSL	0	01 Sept. 2015 – 31 Oct. 2015
MPI	0	01 Sept. 2015 – 31 Oct. 2015
CERFACS	0	01 Sept. 2015 – 31 Oct. 2015
Total	1	

Total estimated effort for this deliverable (DoA) was 1 person-month.

10. Sustainability

10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Within ESIWACE we have established a network of communication and public relations officers. Most of the institutions in the partnership have already a *communication or press office* in place, which is in charge of releasing press communications through well-established channels and networks. Support from their side has been determinant in the formulation of this document and is deemed to be crucial for a successful implementation of our communication plan, especially to raise attention to upcoming events and results and outcomes of ESIWACE.

10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

A close cooperation has been established with the partners involved in WP1 and WP2, mostly involved in the communication with the European HPC ecosystem actors as well as in the implementation of the workshops. In these first two months of activity, we got in contact with the network of other European funded initiatives in HPC: other centres of excellence, FET HPC projects, EXDCI, ETP4HPC, PRACE and with the relevant services at the European Commission. We have indicated our availability to engage with these networks and to support their communication activities, since we target the same communities.

11. Dissemination activities

Add the dissemination activities related to this deliverable.

Not applicable to this specific deliverable.

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1. Introduction

Among the major objectives of ESIWACE are to foster and steer collaboration, communication and co-development within the Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and climate modelling community.

In order to effectively maintain and raise the interest and to evoke some further actions the project has to reach different types of audiences beyond the project partners - they determine the methodologies and relevant media to communicate with them. The content of the information and the way the information is conveyed have to be specific for the different target groups. In this document, we outline different strategies and adequate tools of communication for reaching these audiences.

The general objectives that determine the key components of the ESIWACE Media and Communication Plan (MCP) are:

- To ensure high visibility of ESIWACE by matching the appropriate communication channel to the specific audience and formulating a strategy on how to, accordingly, most effectively disseminate project results;
- To design specific actions resulting in sustainable community building in the field of NWP and climate research;
- To engage and ensure collaboration with industry;
- To contribute to the growth of skills within the partner communities;
- To ensure that all project partners can identify the specific needs of each target audience and tailor their information accordingly;

2. Target audiences

1. Project partners¹
2. Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)
3. User Group Committee (UGC)
4. Supporters
5. Scientific NWP and climate research community
6. Other EU- funded projects/initiatives and networks
7. Other scientific networks
8. Business Sector (Hardware Vendors, SMEs)
9. Policy makers
10. European Commission services
11. Press and media
12. General public

For different types of audiences, we have identified the following:

- Specific goals of the communication measures
- Language register
- Tools: i.e. the list of best communication tools tailored for the specific audience
- Potential contents
- Frequency
- Responsibilities within the consortium

For each communication tool, we have provided a short description and a number of possible indicators for monitoring the outcome of the activity. Some of these tools are already operative.

¹ These are the partners i.e. the beneficiaries who signed the grant agreement and the consortium agreement.

Audience 1: Project partners

Goals of the communication measure

- Supporting knowledge exchange and collaboration within the consortium at all levels
- Ensuring smooth exchange of information for efficient project implementation and management
- Supporting the project management

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Project intranet [D5.1] <https://www.esiwace.eu/partners/access-the-intranet> (redmine)
- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- General Assembly meetings
- Annual project meetings
- Telcos / web-meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Work package meetings
- Progress reports
- Deliverables and other reports
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Infographics

Potential contents

- Results of work packages/ tasks and further implications of these
- Identification of foreseen and (potential) unforeseen risks for the project outcomes
- Queries from users outside the project
- Newly arising scientific questions

Frequency

Regular updates on biweekly basis

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, MSB, supported by the project office

Involvement: all

Audience 2: Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)

Goals of the communication measure

- Informing SAB about ESiWACE activities and communities needs, achieved results and used methods
- Getting Allowing advice and steering from the SAB, thus increasing efficiency in implementation

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Project intranet [D5.1] <https://www.esiwace.eu/partners/access-the-intranet> (redmine)
- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Project annual meetings
- SAB meetings
- Telcos / web-meetings
- Project workshops
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Progress Reports
- Deliverable and other Reports
- Infographics

Potential contents

- Results of work packages/tasks
- Assessment of risks for the project outcome and corresponding prevention/mitigation measures
- Newly arising scientific questions

Frequency

Monthly basis

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 3: User Group Committee (UGC)

Goals of the communication measure

- Broadening the ESIWACE basis in terms of users, contributors and scope
- Potentially attracting other groups, linked to the UGC, to actively follow the development of ESIWACE
- Ensuring integration and engagement of wide parts of the NWP and climate research community
- Communicating achieved results and used methods
- Soliciting feedback on upcoming needs, questions, problems at any time

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Progress reports
- Deliverable and other Reports
- Telcos/web-meetings, Project Annual Meetings, Work package meetings
- Project workshops
- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Guidelines and training material
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Infographics
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect) <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>
-

Potential contents

- Information on status and/or solutions for problems UGC drew to the attention of ESIWACE
- Results of work packages/ tasks and implications
- Guidelines and training material
- Identification and assessment of risks for the project outcomes
- Queries from users outside the project
- Newly arising scientific and technical questions
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Quarterly

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 4: ESIWACE Supporters

Goals of the communication measure

- Broadening the ESIWACE users' basis
- Attracting more groups to actively follow the development of ESIWACE
- Ensuring integration and engagement of wide parts of the NWP and climate research community
- Communicating achieved results and used methods
- Soliciting feedback on upcoming needs, questions, problems at any time

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Annual project meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Deliverables and other reports
- Guidelines and training material
- Progress reports
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Press releases
- Infographics
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect) <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>

Potential contents

- Results of work package tasks
- Newly arising scientific questions
- Public Guidelines and training material
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Semiannual

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 5: Scientific Numerical Weather Prediction and Climate Modelling Community

As indicated in the project description of the action, ESIWACE is built upon an existing scientific network from NWP and climate modelling community. The network consists of 16 direct partners and beneficiaries and of a group of 39 supporting institutions and networks willing to contribute and interact with ESIWACE. Each partner and supporter is partner of other projects and networks, at national, European, and global level. There are a number of other projects dealing partly with topics addressed by ESIWACE. Contacts have already been established with some of these, harmonizing communication strategies and sharing tools.

Goals of the communication measure

- Widening the participation and encouraging the different groups to contribute to ESIWACE actively
- Raising the awareness of the scientific community and visibility for the project results
- Sharing relevant project progress, results and knowledge
- Establishing new contacts to interested parties external to the project thus to get an insider view about their ongoing activities
- Sharing the understanding of research targets
- Discussing consequences of achieved results and learning about new developments relevant for the project progress

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Annual project meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Deliverables and other reports
- Guidelines and training material
- Progress reports
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Press releases
- Infographics
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect) <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>

Potential contents

- Results of work package tasks
- New scientific questions arising

- Public guidelines and training material
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Semiannual

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 6: Other EU- funded projects/initiatives and networks

Goals of the communication measure

- Widening the participation and encouraging the different groups to interact with ESIWACE
- Exploring points of contact for scientific cooperation
- Sharing relevant project progress, results and knowledge
- Interacting toward the creation of seamless infrastructure interfaces in Europe
- Raising awareness of the scientific community on and visibility for the project results
- Discussing consequences of archived results and learning about new developments relevant for the project progress

Language register

For specialists and non-specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect) <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>
- Annual project meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Public deliverables and other reports
- Guidelines and training material
- Progress reports
- Press releases
- Infographics
- Twitter account @esiwace

Potential contents

- Results of work package tasks
- New scientific questions arising
- Public guidelines and training material
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Semiannual

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the project office

Involvement: all

Audience 7: Other scientific networks

Goals of the communication measure

- Sharing relevant project progress and knowledge
- Widening the participation and encourage the different groups to interact with ESIWACE
- Exploring points of contact for scientific cooperation
- Raising the awareness of the scientific community and visibility for the project results
- Discussing consequences of archived results and learning about new developments relevant for the project progress

Language register

For specialists and non-specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Annual project meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Deliverables and other reports
- Guidelines and training material
- Progress reports
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Press releases
- Public Lectures
- Infographics
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect)
<https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>

Potential contents

- Results of work package tasks
- New scientific questions arising
- Public Guidelines and training material
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Semiannual

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 8: Business Sector

Examples: Hardware vendors

Goals of the communication measure

- Sharing relevant project progress and knowledge
- Establishing new contacts
- Getting inputs on establishing possible directions towards sustainability
- Ensuring maximum benefit for project partners and business sector
- Indirectly stimulating growth and competitiveness

Language register

For specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Annual project meetings
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Public deliverables and other reports
- Guidelines and training material
- Progress reports
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Press releases
- Infographics

Potential contents

- Results of work package tasks
- Development of foreseen and (potential) unforeseen risks for the project outcome
- New scientific questions arising
- Public guidelines and training material
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Semiannual

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, CNRS-IPSL (WP1), MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 9: Policy makers

Goals of the communication measure

- Raising the awareness on project goals and results
- Fostering exploitation of results outside the project
- Enhancing impacts of the project beyond the project core community

Language register

For non-specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Direct mailing to Member States representatives (Ministry level)
- Policy briefings
- Conference participation
- Abstracts of progress reports
- Interviews and lectures
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Infographics
- Factsheets
- Press releases

Potential contents

- Relevant new findings
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Yearly

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 10: European Commission services

Goals of the communication measure

- Fostering exploitation of results outside the project
- Sharing relevant outcomes of ESIWACE
- Sharing information about ESIWACE events
- Ensuring visibility of ESIWACE

Language register

For non-specialists

Tools

- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Annual project meetings
- Telcos / web-meetings
- Progress reports
- Deliverables and other reports
- Project workshops
- Conference participation
- Peer-reviewed articles
- Guidelines and training material
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Press releases
- Factsheets
- Infographics
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect)
<https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>

Potential contents

- Relevant new findings
- Links to other relevant web content

Frequency

Yearly

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 11: Press and media

Goals of the communication measure

- Ensuring the visibility of the project
- Sharing relevant outcomes of ESiWACE
- Sharing information about ESiWACE events

Language register

Depending on the target audience of the media

Tools

- Direct mailing to media contacts
- Annual project meetings
- Press releases
- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Conference participation
- Interviews and lectures
- Infographics
- Factsheets
- Storify
- YouTube/Vimeo
- Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect)
<https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science>

Potential contents

- Summaries of relevant project results and implications
- Video materials
- Links to other relevant web content
- FAQ

Frequency

In correspondence of publication of papers, results, events of the community

Examples of media

Responsibilities

Lead: Coordination, MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

Audience 12: General public

Goals of the communication measure

- Raising interest in the project
- Increasing visibility of the project and of its consortium
- Sharing relevant project progress and knowledge

Language register

For non-specialists

Tools

- Communication to this audience will be achieved mainly through web based tools, e.g.
- Website <https://www.esiwace.eu>
- Press releases
- Twitter account @esiwace
- Interviews and lectures
- Infographics
- Factsheets
- Storify
- YouTube/Vimeo
- Participation in the European Researchers' Night

Potential contents

- Lay summaries reporting relevant project results and implications for the society
- Links to relevant web content
- Video materials
- FAQ

Frequency

In correspondence of events organised for the general public

Responsibilities

Coordination, MSB, supported by the Project office

Involvement: all

3. Communication measures

a) Intranet (D5.1)

The project intranet is the only tool that is intended to contain internal information. Thus only ESIWACE partners can get access it. It is based on the DKRZ redmine and contains:

- Internal information, documentation, reports to support the internal communication
- Draft versions of deliverables for cooperate development
- Agendas, invitations to internal meetings, TelCos, WebCos

Access: <https://www.esiwace.eu/partners/access-the-intranet>

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of registered scientists
- Number of downloads

b) Work package meetings

WP meetings will be held on a regular basis within the consortium to ensure smooth project implementation.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of attendees
- Number of interactions in response to events
- Number of preventive/corrective measures introduced for each work package
- Number of reduced risks (assessed during implementation versus identified in the Description of the Action)

c) Project annual meeting

Annual meetings will be held with the goal of allowing interaction between the members of the consortium, the SAB, the UGC and other communities. The ESIWACE General Assembly will be held during the annual project meetings.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of talks
- Number of external guests (not members of the beneficiary organisations)
- Feedback from other communities

d) Project workshops

The workshops will bring together scientists from the consortium with end-users/stakeholders and will be organized for:

- Presentation of project goals
- Identification of stakeholders needs
- Assessment of the suitability of climate forecast parameters for stakeholders' use
- Presentation of success stories within the project
- Presentation of scientific achievements

A minimum of two workshops will be organized during the life time of ESIWACE under the umbrella of ESIWACE - one at the beginning of the project, one at mid-term.

As far as possible, we will record the workshops and make the webcasts available for larger audiences.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of participants from different organisations / communities / networks
- Participants' feedback
- Participants' interest in the project results and products
- Number of participants
- Number of downloads
- Number of viewers

e) Website (D5.2)

The website www.esiwace.eu complies with the Guidelines "EU Project Websites – Best Practice Guidelines (Version March 2010)".

The website contains:

- Description of project goals, consortium, structure and expected outputs to a lay audience
- News
- Guidelines and ESIWACE training material
- A media center: infographics, press releases, factsheets
- Deliverables, reports and publications
- Overview on the most important results of the project
- Information on European HPC ecosystem

Search engines optimization tools will be used for improving ranking, together with a cross linking strategy to and from other projects' website.

Indicators for monitoring

- Monitoring website traffic through statistics
- Feedback of users

f) Conference participation, lectures and interviews

Objectives and results of ESIWACE will be presented by ESIWACE partners and scientists with two goals in mind:

- Getting feedback of the scientific community for evaluation of the scientific quality of the project and re-targeting goals and activities accordingly
- Raising awareness and increase visibility of planned project activities and of achieved results

The communication will be tailored according to the target audience of the events. We will maximize the interaction/networking possibilities with the scientific community and other H2020 projects, and, if possible, we will try to implement specific ESIWACE sessions within established scientific conferences.

Indicators for monitoring

- Participants' feedback

- Number of participants
- Integration of feedback in the project outputs

g) Peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals

It is expected that the project will result in a number of publications in scientific, peer-reviewed journals, especially during the final year of its lifetime. Project partners have been encouraged to strive for joint publications. ESIWACE scientists will share with the Project Office the details on their submitted peer-reviewed articles together with 1) the contact name, 2) an email of the corresponding scientists, 3) a short abstract and 4) indication of the embargo time. The corresponding authors can be contacted at any time by those who are interested in the submitted paper.

- List of published peer-reviewed articles will be available in the Commission portal
- Publications will be made available in OpenAire and ZENODO

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of scientific publications
- Number of views
- Number of downloads

h) Publications in reports and books

Project partners are encouraged to publish their results in other edited books or reports during and after the project's lifespan.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of publications
- Feedback of the scientific community

i) Twitter

Our account is [@esiwace](#). The account will be used to interact with several actors, automatically reporting about it, and to launch news related to the project.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of followers
- Number of retweets
- Number of tweets marked as "favourite" by other users

j) Deliverable, progress reports, and other reports

Deliverables and reports will be made available on the website and in ZENODO if they have a public status. If not, they will be made available in the intranet.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of views
- Number of downloads
- Number of further interactions with external parties such as requests for more information and materials, requests for contacts to the scientific teams and similar.

k) Factsheets

- We will create a factsheet at the beginning of the project **highlighting the main features of the project**. Updates will be made available on the website at regular intervals. Presentation of the project activities, partnership, goals and impacts will be made available for the public in a language understandable for a lay audience. Factsheets will be available for download on the website. Paper copies will be printed and distributed to partners for further dissemination activities at major events.
- Easy-reading summaries of main results / project outcomes will be made available by short reports of 1-2 pages – in a language understandable for a lay audience. These will allow the general public and policy makers to gain an understanding of the report's contents and to decide if they need to read the report as a whole.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of downloads / views
- Feedback of the general public / stakeholders / community
- Monitoring volume of posts, comments and followers
- Users / communities / Stakeholders' feedback

l) Direct mailing to press and media

Contacts will be sought primarily with the following specific magazines:

- **Primeur magazine:** For over 20 years this magazine has been communicating about HPC and related distributed technologies for companies, as dissemination experts in European research projects and as publisher of the oldest magazine on supercomputing and HPC in the world. The magazine disseminates to: high-tech companies, to scientists, European Commission, general, technical and public media, including printed media, television and online. <http://primeurmagazine.com/>
- **Inside HPC:** Founded on December 28, 2006, insideHPC is a blog that distills news and events in the world of HPC and presents them in bite-sized nuggets of helpfulness as a resource for supercomputing professionals. <http://insidehpc.com/>
- **Scientific computing world:** The only global publication dedicated to the computing and information technology needs of scientists and engineers. It covers computing for engineering, science, and technology, grouped under the headings of Informatics, High-Performance Computing, and Application software. **High-Performance Computing** is central to the publication, with a special section in the print magazine and an e-newsletter devoted to HPC. <http://www.scientific-computing.com/>
- **HPC wire:** Since its inception in 1986, HPC has enjoyed a legacy of world-class editorial and topnotch journalism, making it the portal of choice selected by science, technology and business professionals interested in high performance and data-intensive computing <http://www.hpcwire.com/>

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of articles based on our inputs
- Feedback and requests of journalists

m) Press releases

Press releases are drafted in correspondence of events and relevant outcome of the project.

Channels for press releases will be:

- Press and communication officers of the partners
- Press and communication channels of the EC (DG Connect)
- Press and communication channels of other EU funded initiative and networks
- AlphaGalileo <http://www.alphagalileo.org/> Internet press center for European science, engineering and technology.
- EurekaAlert <http://www.eurekaalert.org/> online science news service featuring health, medicine, science and technology news from leading research institutions and universities.
- Twitter
- LinkedIn

Additionally, similar channels at national level will be used by our partners in their countries.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of requests /downloads / views
- Feedback and requests of journalists

n) Storify

Storify is the easiest way to find, collect, and share what people are saying all over the web.

Social networks can make anyone an on-the-spot source as events unfold. Storify helps finding the best first-hand reports anywhere in the world for the next story, for breaking the news and without character limits <https://storify.com/>

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of views
- Number of shares

o) Infographics

High Performance Computing Goes Mainstream

High-powered technical computing increasingly is used to solve practical problems in manufacturing, life sciences, oil and gas, and other industries, but many companies still aren't fully tapping its potential.

Technical computing achievements

The **Boeing Company** aims to use simulations to redesign the vertical tail of a commercial jet, potentially saving **\$300 million** in fuel costs annually.

Using IBM technical computing, **Vestas Wind Systems** reduced their wind turbine placement analysis from weeks to less than **one hour**.

Red Bull Racing used IBM technical computing software to simulate new car designs and achieved a **20% increase** in performance and throughput, coming up with a design that reduces their cars' drag on the track.

¹ Intersect 300
² NCMS

Infographics can be used to portray data, statistics, facts, information and reports effectively, especially for lay audiences. Increasingly in science, infographics are being used to break down and simplify complex messages. Infographics can be embedded in every document (reports, infosheets) and media tools (Twitter and Pinterest for instance)² *Pinterest* is a visual bookmarking tool that helps discover and save creative ideas, it is widely used by lay audiences to discover thousands of images about Science.

Example:

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/high-performance-computing-europe>

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of downloads
- Number of views
- Number of favourites
- Number of retweets
- Number of pins

² <http://blogs.nature.com/ofschemasandmemes/2014/01/20/the-power-of-using-infographics-to-communicate-science>

- Number of likes
- Number of followers

p) European Researchers' nights

The European Researchers' Night takes place each year. Whether with family, friends, school, everybody will have the opportunity to become a scientist for a day, discover different scientific disciplines and, most of all, have fun. All the events take place simultaneously in 280 cities across Europe and beyond. We will take part in this event by offering talks about the core of our research.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of participants attending the talks

q) YouTube/ Vimeo

Video materials related to contributions and interventions to conferences will be channelled via YouTube and Vimeo.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of downloads
- Number of views
- Number of favourites
- Number of likes
- Number of followers

r) Digital4Science platform of the EC

Digital4Science is a virtual space created by the European Commission for dialogue open to all in the fields of Open Science, Future and Emerging Technologies, and e-Infrastructure. The platform is available here: [#https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science](https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science) #D4science
Digital4Science focuses on two main areas:

- 1) co-operation between projects, enabling current projects to share experiences and best practices
- 2) getting ready for work programme 2016-17

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of uploads
- Number of views
- Number of favourites
- Number of ratings
- Number of interactions with other users of the platform

s) Policy briefings and direct mailing to Member States representatives

Policy briefings are meant in the sense of reports or ad hoc meetings with Member States representatives/policy makers.

Indicators for monitoring

- Number of participants
- Participants' feedback
- Integration of feedback in the project outputs
- Number of requests /downloads / views

- Feedback and requests of journalists
- Number of interactions following up briefings/direct mailing

4. Matrix Audiences and Tools

Audiences Communication measures	Business Sector	European Commission services	General public	Other EU-funded projects/initiatives and networks	Other scientific networks	Policy makers	Press and media	Project partners	Scientific Advisory Board	Scientific Numerical Weather Prediction and Climate Research Community	Supporters	User Group Committee
Project intranet (redmine)								Yes	Yes			
Annual project meetings	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
General Assembly meetings								Yes				
SAB meetings									Yes			
Work package meetings								Yes				Yes
Guidelines and Training Material	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes					Yes	Yes	Yes
Project workshops	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Website https://www.esiwace.eu	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Conference participation, Interviews and lectures	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Public Lectures					Yes							
Peer-reviewed articles	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Twitter account @esiwace	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes
Public deliverables and other reports	Yes			Yes								
Abstracts of progress reports						Yes						
Progress Reports	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Deliverables and other reports		Yes			Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Factsheets		Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes					
Direct mailing to media contacts							Yes					
Press releases	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	
Storify			Yes				Yes					

Audiences Communication measures	Business Sector	European Commission services	General public	Other EU-funded projects/initiatives and networks	Other scientific networks	Policy makers	Press and media	Project partners	Scientific Advisory Board	Scientific Numerical Weather Prediction and Climate Research Community	Supporters	User Group Committee
Infographics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Participation in the European Researchers' Night			Yes									
YouTube/Vimeo			Yes				Yes					
Digital4Science platform of the European Commission (DG Connect) https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/digital4science		Yes		Yes	Yes		Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes
Policy briefings						Yes						
Direct mailing to Member States representatives (Ministry level)						Yes						

5. List of acronyms

CNRS – IPSL	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique – Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace
DKRZ	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum
D	Deliverable
ESIWACE	Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
MSB	Management Steering Board
MCP	Media and Communication Plan
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
UGC	User Group Committee
WP	Work package